

Stochastics Analysis of Cement Manufacturing using Exponential Distribution¹

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Abstract

The primary goal of every industry in the current competitive market environment is to increase equipment performance while lowering operating costs. This work uses the regenerating point technique and the Semi-Markov process to build a stochastic model. Here, a cement industry machine with a complicated configuration and numerous subsystems where various problems arise during operation is used. A system's parametric values are mostly determined by the subsystem's failure and repair rates. Here in the cement industry, a system of a two units (P&Q) is considered in which one unit having subsystems connected in parallel and second unit having subsystems connected in series. In this paper, if unit P in which subsystem are connected in parallel then if one or more subsystems fail then system works in reduced capacity and if the system is considered to be fail then the system is considered to be in the failed state. On the other hand, the second unit Q in which all the subsystems are connected in series then if any of its subsystem fail then the unit fail causing the whole system in failed state. This study will use mathematical techniques such as MTSF/MTBF, Markov chain, Markov process, renewal process, and others to evaluate the system and derive various dependability metrics.

Keywords

Markov process Mean Time to system failure, Markov chain, , renewal process Regenerative Point, Availability, Busy Period.

Introduction

Because of the speed at which technology is changing in today's business and industry, many researchers have focused on reliability by examining two systems under different assumptions. Different authors use different sets of assumptions and different kinds of repair policies, and repair is one of the most crucial metrics for boosting a system's effectiveness. The stochastic analysis of two non-identical cement manufacturing units is the subject of this research. The cement production

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machine is made up of several subsystems that operated in parallel and series configurations. The intricate process of making cement starts with the extraction and grinding of raw ingredients, known as raw meal, which is subsequently heated to a sintering temperature. There are four steps in the entire cement manufacturing process.

Mixing of raw material = There are two ways to mix: wet process and dry process. Gyratory crushers are used to smash raw materials in the dry process. To obtain fine particles, the crushed materials are ground once again. The initial step in the wet process is crushing the raw materials, turning them into power, and then storing them in silos. After that, clay is cleaned, sticky organic materials are eliminated, and it is transferred to grinding mills.

Burning = The raw materials are rotated at their longitudinal axis during this procedure in a rotary kiln. From the upper end of the kiln, the dry process raw mix of the corrected wet process slurry is injected. From the burning zone, the clinker is extremely hot. At the base of the rotary kiln, air is admitted in a countercurrent direction to lower the temperature of the clinkers. Tiny trolleys are used to gather the cooled clinkers.

Grinding = The cooled clinkers are received from the cooling pans and sent into mills. The clinkers are grinding finely into powder in ball mill. The final obtained product is cement.

Storage and packing = The grinded cement is stored in silos, from which it is marketed in bags.

In this paper, from a cement industry a system of a two units (P&Q) is considered in which one unit having subsystems connected in parallel and second unit having subsystems connected in series. In this paper, if unit P in which subsystem are connected in parallel then if one or more subsystems fail then system works in reduced capacity and if the system is considered to be fail then the system is considered to be in the failed state. On the other hand, the second unit Q in which all the subsystems are connected in series then if any of its subsystem fail then the unit fail causing the whole system in failed state. A single repair facility appears in and disappears from the system randomly with constant rate. In this paper, system will be analyzed to calculate the several reliability measures by using mathematical tools MTSF/MTBF, Markov chain, Markov process, renewal process etc.

Description of system and Assumption:-

- In this model, a repairable system having two units is to be considered. Initially both units are taken in good state.
- It is considered that unit P has subsystems those are connected in parallel. Hence if one or more subsystems fail then system works in reduced capacity.
- Also it is considered Unit P is fail that if all the subsystems of unit P are fail.
- All the subsystems of unit Q are considered to be connected in series. So if one subsystem is fail then unit is considered to be failed.
- It is considered that the repairman repair the partially failed unit P in reduced stage and after repair the subsystem the unit P is starts working as good as new.
- System is considered in Up-state if one unit is working and in down state if no unit is working.
- Each unit of the system has two modes-normal operative or failed.
- Each repair improves efficiency of working of a unit.

- A single server facility is available with the system that maintains and repair the units.
- All the random variable are independent.

3. Notations

E:	Set of regenerative states
\bar{E} :	Set of non-regenerative states
P,Q:	Unit is in operative state
λ_1 :	Invariant failure rate of a unit P
λ_2 :	Invariant failure rate of a unit P from reduced state to complete failure.
λ :	Invariant failure rate of a unit Q
$g(t), \bar{G}(t)$:	pdf and cdf of repair time of a failed unit P from reduced state to working state
$h(t), \bar{H}(t)$:	pdf and cdf of repair time of a unit P from failed to reduced state
$f(t), F(t)$:	pdf and cdf of repair time of a unit P from failed to reduced state
⊗	Symbol for Laplace convolution
⊗	Symbol for Laplace Stieltjes Convolution
○	Up-state
⬡	Partial State
□	Down-state
●	Regenerative Point

The system can be in any of the following states with respect of the above symbols:

$S_0=(P,Q)$	$S_1=(P',Q)$	$S_4=(P',q)$
$S_2=(p,Q)$	$S_3=(P,q)$	

4. Transition Probabilities

The epoch of entry into states $\{S_0, S_1, \dots\}$ are regenerative states. The transition probabilities from the states S_i to S_j are given by Q_{ij} and in the states p_{ij} denotes the transition probability from states S_i to S_j are given under

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_{01} &= \lambda_1 / (\lambda + \lambda_1) & p_{30} &= 1 \\
 p_{03} &= \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_1) & p_{20} &= 1 \\
 p_{10} &= g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2) = 1 & p_{41} &= 1 \\
 p_{14} &= \lambda(-g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2)) / (\lambda + \lambda_2) & p_{12} &= \lambda_2(1 - g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2)) / (\lambda + \lambda_2) = p_1^2 \\
 p_{12} &= \lambda_2(1 - g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2)) / (\lambda + \lambda_2) \\
 p_{14} &= p_1^4
 \end{aligned}$$

It can be easily verified that

$$p_{01} + p_{03} = 1 \quad p_{10} + p_{14} + p_{12} = 1$$

Mean Sojourn Times

Mean Sojourn Times may be defined by

$$\mu_i = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^x P[t: 0 < t > T] dt$$

So that in steady state we have following relations

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_0 &= 1/(\lambda + \lambda_1) & \mu_3 &= -f''(0) \\ \mu_1 &= [1 - g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2)] / (\lambda + \lambda_2) & \mu_4 &= -f''(0) \\ \mu_2 &= -h''(0) \end{aligned}$$

The unconditional mean time taken by the system to transit from any states S_i to S_j is mathematically given by

$$m_{ij} = \int_0^{\infty} t dQ_{ij}(t) = -q_{ij}'(s) \big|_{s=0}$$

So that

$$\begin{aligned} m_{01} &= \lambda_1 / (\lambda + \lambda_1)^2 \\ m_{02} &= \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_1)^2 \\ m_{10} &= -g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2) \\ m_{14} &= \lambda [1 - g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2)] / (\lambda + \lambda_2)^2 + \lambda g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2) / (\lambda + \lambda_2) \\ m_{12} &= \lambda_2 [1 - g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2)] / (\lambda + \lambda_2)^2 + \lambda_2 g^*(\lambda + \lambda_2) / (\lambda + \lambda_2) \end{aligned}$$

It can be easily verified that

$$\begin{aligned} m_{01} + m_{03} &= 1 / (\lambda + \lambda_1) = \mu_0 \\ m_{10} + m_{12} + m_{14} &= \mu_1 \end{aligned}$$

Mean Time to System Failure

The mean time to system failure is given by the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_0(t) &= q_{01}(t) \otimes \Omega_1(t) + Q_{03}(t) \\ \Omega_1(t) &= q_{10}(t) \otimes \Omega_0(t) + Q_{12}(t) + Q_{14}(t) \end{aligned}$$

Solving above equation by taking Laplace Stieltjes transformations and solving for $\Omega_0^{**}(s)$, we get

$$\Omega_0^{**}(s) = \frac{N(s)}{D(s)}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} N(s) &= q_{03} + q_{01}(q_{12} + q_{14}) \\ D(s) &= 1 - q_{01}q_{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$MTSF = \Omega_0 = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} [(1 - \Omega_0^{**}(s))/s] = \{D'(0) - N'(0)\} / D(0)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} D'(0) - N'(0) &= \mu_0 + \mu_1 p_{01} \\ D(0) &= 1 - p_{01} p_{10} \end{aligned}$$

Availability of the system

The point wise availability $\mathbb{A}V_i(t)$ of the system is given by

$$\mathbb{A}V_0(t) = \dot{M}_0(t) + q_{01}(t) \otimes \mathbb{A}V_1(t) + q_{03}(t) \otimes \mathbb{A}V_0(t)$$

$$\dot{A}V_1(t) = \dot{M}_1(t) + q_{10}(t) \odot AV_0(t) + q_1^{(4)}(t) + q_1^{(2)}(t) \odot AV_0(t)$$

Now taking Laplace transform of these equations and solving them for $AV_0^*(s)$, we get

$$AV_0^*(s) = \frac{N_1(s)}{D_1(s)}$$

The steady states availability is given by

$$AV_0^{**} = \lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} (s AV_0^*(s)) = \frac{N_1(0)}{D_1'(0)}$$

Where

$$\dot{M}_0(t) = \mu_0 \quad \dot{M}_1(t) = \mu_1$$

$$N_1(0) = \mu_0(1 - p_{14}) + \mu_1(t) p_{01}$$

And

$$D_1(0) = 0$$

$$D_1'(0) = \mu_0(1 - p_{14}) + \mu_1(t) p_{01}$$

Busy Period for Repairman-

$$B_0(t) = q_{01}(t) \odot B_1(t) + q_0^{(3)}(t) \odot B_0(t) + W_1(t)$$

$$B_1(t) = q_{10}(t) \odot B_0(t) + q_1^{(4)}(t) \odot B_1(t) + q_1^{(2)}(t) \odot B_0(t) + W_2(t)$$

The Repair time $R\check{T}_i(t)$ of the system is given by

Now taking Laplace transform of these equations and solving them for $BP_0(s)$, we get

The repair time is given by

$$BP_0^*(s) = [N_2(s) / D_1(s)]$$

$$BP_0^{**} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} (s R\check{T}_0^*(s)) = [N_2(0) / D_1(0)]$$

$$N_2(0) = W_1(1 - p_{14}) + W_2 p_{01}$$

Where

$$W_1 = \int_0^t e^{(\lambda + \lambda_1)t} G(t) dt$$

$$W_1 = \int_0^t e^{(\lambda + \lambda_1)t} F(t) dt$$

And

$D_1'(0)$ is already defined

Profit Function of the system-

$$P_0(t) = C_1 A_0 - C_2 B_0 - C_3 V_0$$

Particular cases:

If we take repair rate and inspection time as negative binomial distributions as

$$h(t) = \mu e^{-\mu t}$$

$$g(t) = \rho e^{-\rho t}$$

Then we get,

$\rho_{01} = \lambda_1 / (\lambda + \lambda_1)$	$\rho_{30} = 1$
$\rho_{03} = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_1)$	$\rho_{20} = 1$
$\rho_{10} = \rho / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)$	$\rho_{41} = 1$
$\rho_{14} = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)$	$\rho_{12} = \rho_{1^2_0} = \lambda_2 / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)$
$\rho_{12} = \lambda_2 / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)$	$\rho_{14} = \rho_{1^4_3} = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)$
$\mu_0 = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_1)$	$\mu_1 = 1 / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)$
$\mu_2 = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_2)$	$\mu_3 = -f''(0)$
$\mu_4 = -f''(0)$	$m_{01} = \lambda_1 / (\lambda + \lambda_1)^2$
$m_{02} = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_1)^2$	$m_{10} = \rho / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)^2$
$m_{12} = \lambda / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)^2$	$m_{14} = \lambda_2 / (\lambda + \lambda_2 + \rho)^2$
$m_{01} + m_{02} = \mu_0$	$m_{10} + m_{12} + m_{14} = \mu_1$

The expectable outcomes based on above particular cases can be explained with the graphs as following:

Effect of change of Failure Rate of units on MTSF and Availability

Fixing the repair rate $\rho = \sigma = \xi = 0.7$

Varying λ and fixing λ_1 and λ_2 equal to 0.1 and vice versa.

Effect of change of Repair Rate of units on MTSF and Availability

Fixing the repair rate $\lambda = \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.1$

Varying ρ and fixing σ and ξ equal to 0.7 and vice versa.

$\lambda = \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.1$

$\lambda = \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.1$

State Transition Diagrams

- $S_0 = (P, Q)$
- $S_1 = (P', Q)$
- $S_2 = (p, Q)$
- $S_3 = (P, q)$
- $S_4 = (P', q)$

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